

screening detected differences in resistance levels more precisely. For example, in this and in previous field studies, Bogor 8 has always been more resistant than Bogor 1 and the other 10 Bogor lines (not included in the table). Also, Mudgo, whose greenhouse reactions to biotype 2 are generally similar to those

of IR26 (susceptible, as both have BPH 1 gene), exhibits more resistance in the field.

Insect pressure was extremely high at 95 DT in the field screening and only the highly resistant lines such as CR157-392-284, CR179-1-717, IET 5120, IET 5122, ARC 6650, ARC 14529, and

the photosensitive varieties Babawee, Rathu Heenati, and Ptb 33 were resistant.

More varieties and breeding lines with resistance to biotype 2 and with multigenic resistance to several biotypes need to be included in the 1978 IRBPHN.

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GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Deep water

Stem borer incidence in deep-water rice

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Studies on deep-water rice in Bangladesh in 1977 revealed a surprisingly high incidence of stem borers in the vegetative phase of the crop (Apr. to mid-Sept.). The investigations involved regular pest surveys of farmers' fields in deep-water rice areas and an intensive study of the population dynamics of stem borers in two fields in Keraniganj and Manikganj, Dacca district. Stem borer incidence was assessed mainly by dissecting individual stems (usually 100 to 200 stems), and

also by counting egg masses and moths.

Stem borer larvae were found in each of 24 dissections from fields in Comilla, Dacca, Faridpur, Noakhali, Pabna, and Tangail districts. In 71% of the dissections, more than 10% of the stems were infested; in 33%, more than 20% were infested.

At the population dynamics site at Keraniganj, from late June to mid-September, the incidence of infested stems varied from 20 to 38%; at Manikganj it varied from 36 to 47%. In a new deep-water tank at Joydebpur planted to the variety Habiganj Aman II, 52% of the stems had been attacked by early September.

In a quick survey of some deep-water rice areas in Thailand, Burma, and India, stem borers were the most important pest; more than 10% of the stems were infested in several fields.

The yellow stem borer *Tryporyza incertulas* was constantly the dominant species and appears well-adapted to deep-water rice. Larvae feed in the hollow section of the stem. Because this section is usually submerged, the activity is not reflected by deadheart incidence; some dissections showed more than 30% infested stems without a single deadheart. For that reason, and because rising floodwater can submerge deadhearts in a few days, early and midseason stem borer damage in deep-water rice has probably been overlooked and thus underestimated in the past.

We do not yet know the effect of high levels of early stem damage, but yields are probably lowered. With the manifold problems of using insecticides on deep-water rice, the yellow stem borer presents a considerable challenge to breeders and entomologists. W

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Adverse soils

Aluminum toxicity and phosphorus deficiency in acid sulfate soils of Thailand

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Broadcast rice with symptoms that resembled those described for aluminum toxicity were observed in the eastern Bangkok Plain (between Pathum Thani and Nakhon Nayok) in June 1977. Older leaves had an orange-yellow discoloration along the margins and sometimes between the veins. Most plants also suffered from

moderate to severe phosphorus deficiency.

This deep-water rice area (about 0.25 million ha) has moderately acid sulfate soils (pH 4.0–4.7). The symptoms were most noticeable with increasing

acidity (4.0–4.3) and plants were almost dead in a field where road construction had removed the surface soil and exposed the highly acid subsoil.

Rice in the area is broadcast after the first rains in April or May, but flooding

Chemical analysis of plant samples. Eastern Bangkok Plain, Thailand.

	Elements			
	Fe (ppm)	Al (ppm)	K (%)	P (%)
Affected plants	309	911	0.93	0.031
Healthy plants	175	171	2.21	0.069
Normal levels	< 300	< 300	> 1.0	> 0.1

does not begin until June or July. Because the crop grows in dry soil for 2 to 4 months, it does not benefit from the increase in pH on flooding, which lowers the harmful levels of aluminum.

Plants of the traditional variety Nang Kiew with orange-yellow discolorations were sampled on 23 June near Bang-or. The crop had been broadcast on 10 May

on soil classified as Sulfic Tropaquept. The affected plants had higher aluminum and lower phosphorus contents than healthy plants from the same field.

Aluminum toxicity in wetland rice has received relatively little attention because the high amount of dissolved aluminum normally disappears soon after flooding, even on very acid soils. Aluminum

toxicity may be a major factor limiting production in deep-water rice an acid sulfate soils as long as good irrigation facilities are lacking and no fertilizer is applied. Introduction of varieties adapted to high aluminum and low phosphorus should help increase rice production in the area. **W**

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

International rice testing program

Three IRTP monitoring tours in 1977

In 1977, the International Rice Testing Program (IRTP) sponsored three monitoring tours to enable rice scientists from various countries to observe the performance of materials from different sources in the international nurseries and to become better acquainted with other rice research in the regions.

The first tour focused on rice in the arid regions. All participants visited Sudan, Egypt, and Pakistan, and several visited Punjab state, India. The group observed the vast potential for rice production in the region and similar breeding objectives in various countries in the region. They noted that many current IRTP entries from the humid tropics were not suited to the region and that active local breeding programs were developing promising materials. The group therefore recommended the establishment of an International Rice Arid Regions Observational Nursery (IRARON) where national programs in the region could enter their best rices along with selected entries from IRRI and other IRTP nurseries. Entries should have the following traits: high yielding ability; long, slender grain (scented and nonscented); early maturity (110 – 130 days); tolerance to salinity, alkalinity, and zinc deficiency; early growth vigor; resistance to stem borer, blast, and brown spot; and tolerance to high temperature. Dr. M. S. Balal of Egypt will pack and dispatch the nurseries to interested arid-region scientists in March 1978. The IRTP will make field books and analyze and publish the results. Those

Scientists on the IRTP monitoring tour to East India and Nepal inspecting an International Upland Rice Observational Nursery at the Rice Research Station, Ranchi, Bihar, India.

interested in conducting the nursery should contact the Joint Coordinator of IRTP at IRRI.

The second IRTP monitoring tour focused on rice improvement in Nepal and northern India. In Nepal's Kathmandu Valley, varieties need some cold tolerance and blast resistance. The Tarai area of Nepal is similar to Bihar state, India, where bacterial blight is a major constraint. Drought was the major problem in southern Bihar and in the Faizabad area of eastern Uttar Pradesh, India. Gall midge was a major constraint around Cuttack and Bhubaneswar, India. The group recommended earlier dispatch of the IRTP nurseries to enable timely planting at all locations. They also

recommended entries for the 1978 nurseries and discussed some improvements in the methodology and conduct of future IRTP nurseries.

The third tour was after an IRTP planning conference for Latin America, held at the International Center for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT) in Colombia. It focused on upland rice in Central America and Mexico. The group noted the favorable rainfall patterns and soil types in the region. Yields of many varieties often reached 5 to 6 t/ha. Blast, sheath blight, and leaf scald damaged some varieties considerably at certain locations. The group recommended that efforts to develop varieties with stable blast resistance for the region be